

VIRTUALIZATION IN THE TRAINING OF ENGINEERS AS A FACTOR OF INCREASING SCIENTIFIC EFFICIENCY

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Abstract: *These components of virtuality are indispensable parts of new education technologies in itself represent Virtual modeling and virtual technologies visual images objective truth with tie up for new factor, time extent of time reverse rotation, unreal situations modeling like factors with is described.*

Keywords: *technological, virtual, compare, information*

Today's to the day come, information communicative of technologies without example development as a result mann the fieldsain new to achievements is being achieved. In our opinion, from ICT edtotem improvement in order to use too very important is consnformation society society of life social, economic, political on the fronts virtuality high level done increase demonstration is doing and this whole society life virtualization from the trend proof gives Education system virtualization technological in terms of news approach based on is, it is virtual information field, virtual education models, virtual education technologies, virtual information structures and information fromThis componenttent found. Thiare s components opartsrtuality indispensable part as new education technologies in itself represents Virtual modeling and virtual technologies visual images objective truth with tie up for new factor, time extent of time reverse rotation, unreal situations modeling like factors with is described [1]. Big information capacity own into received information of s created these space scopemodels appear to be virtual education for addition opportunities created Virtual education technology is this student and study source virtual information between mutually effect in the process information and telecommunications from technologies used without done to be increased new education from technologies one is considered Virtual education to himself special

feature is this teacher with student and virtual reality in the middle of the intermediary lack of This technology active entrepreneurship to the game based on learning with let's compare can Virtual education advantages most of the time multimedia teaching of means use possibilities with justified [2]. Mediation of virtual education basis is now traditional of education necessary to the element is spinning. Around of events diversity and they are between connections in the mind of images different structures to the body to bring can of course, reality reflection carry on methods possible as long as polymorphic to be need That's why for, information of influence complexity, that is information mediation If he does, he accepts of the doer in his mind information-mental to structures effect to do point of view in terms of to the communicant so much big effect shows. new in Uzbekistan pedagogy science innovative development perspectives: theory and practice of the process consistency of teaching content, forms, methods and of means unity mean holds [3]. If the study of the material content improve for him systematization, actualization and problematic make, forms work exit for - teaching activation, in methodology - individualization and automation important tasks if so, pedagogical tools improvement for today's in the day the most important task is recognized as visualization. Also study of the material visualization, information area and in particular, education mediation hasa been modern global cultural of the trend important structural we consider it a part [3]. Simplified, of course in one discipline education content each how elements:

- a) activity methods to know
- b) activity methods have to be
- c) this activity kind of creativity experience;
- d) to the process and activity as a result emotional - valuable in relation to be experience - general in the case of , an ideal one without - professional activity images system through expression can then this of images each different ratio professional situations organize does teacher them problematic makes them solution to do for tasks makes and that's it with professional thinking of students develops. But to the students emotional the effect of strengthening more big reserves oral not

but visual effect to do in the means they are didactic point of view by implication, property - perception to reach in the eye holder information of products effect one of time in itself different feelings through syncretization own into takes Students intuition to the authorities complicated effect due to, the second known the mood creates, creative thinking develops and perception to be done information size significant level increases. Study area to virtualization about experiences humanitarian sciences according to modern studies the results account received without transfer it is necessary Last in years social and humanitarian sciences in the field theoretical achievements get stronger, man behavior each different rational and emotional circumstances was studied [4]. Virtual education environment (knowledge environment) appears prerequisites for being the following conditions are: - labor in the market changes (labor market work resources again distribution Demand does); - information in the market changes (scientific - technical development pace acceleration of knowledge constant update Demand does); - new contact of possibilities appear be (contact and of the Internet development long remote information sources to enter possibility will give and contact scope extends); new in Uzbekistan pedagogy science innovative development perspectives : Theory and practice in virtual education one how much typical in the form of information status model (situation model). representing dynamic visual model, scene model, cognitive model, information giving model, space model, visual interface and spatial simulation models there is. It is visible models [5]. From this except invisible models there is being to him the following includes: script model, test model, test check model, service show models, spatial systematic models. That's right work developed virtual education model, intended to the goal faster reach for the key considered, then the following to principles action if done to the goal suitable for: – teaching of the student cognitive activity based on to be – virtual training of the program structure dynamic in part modular to be - static in part information units use. Information of the situation model real conditions simulation to do to the process based on Information to the situation based on conditions formation and of the problem next the solution of students study goals suitable coming competence

forms. So information status powers to master focus need [6]. Real to processes imitation simulation models, them visual present reach and virtual modeling based on done is increased. Virtual education in the process of modeling spatial (geoinformational), situational, dynamic such as special of types our use can Conditional modeling is of students professional competencies formation for real work release situations and processes simulation create. Dynamic visual modeling and the student's virtual situation with information mutually from the effect which uses of the audience decision acceptance doer in the role of real activity feeling complete to form intended active teaching method. Dynamic visual models using teaching technology, actions indicative basis account received without, in real situations actions perform conditions of students knowledge, skill and qualifications formation to the concept based on Lecture and seminar teaching from the methodology different like, two task consistent solution first of all, knowledge transmission, secondly, them apply skills formation [7,8,9]. Dynamic visual models using teaching technology situational, visual and teaching like different models work to exit possibility gives. Information situational model or information status model real object and the real situation reflection makes and being studied processes and tasks content new in Uzbekistan pedagogy science innovative development perspectives: theory and practice forming in this situation describe for heuristic and official of approaches use can Heuristic approach, rule as a situation when studied, his do not go the addition of with of the object complete didn't happen partial description mean holds. This information repeated again work necessary take will come and difficult in the situation decision acceptance to do skills to develop help gives. Official approach of the object complete to the description is based on and of the image analytical and mathematician methods using done is increased. This approach algorithmic again work necessary take will come and in the audience analytical thinking and systematic the analysis to develop help gives [10,11,12]. Summary in place that's it to emphasize maybe education system virtualization traditional in education occurring many to problems solution being, we education for class room, strict defined time, way hustle and bustle, boring, one in temp lecture,

held sent training such as to issues efficient solution as will be seen [13,14]. Moreover, the student's critical, creative to think basis be takes.

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